

Principal registered archaeological finds from the surface in South-Limburg (NL) and adjacent areas. FLINT & NATURAL STONE Part 2a: Lithic cores

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1.1. Introduction

For methods of reporting see part 1 of this series. Part 2a is about lithic cores. Such cores, left in a field almost always are the evidence for tool manufacture at the proper location. This tool production could be either from cores brought in from elsewhere, or from locally mined flint. South Limburg is a flint rich area, with many discoveries in the domain of tool manufacturing industry like the Rijckholt flint mines and many other mining areas in the wider region, often the exploitation points are accompanied by processed (flint) stone tools (Rademakers, 1998). In this part an overview is given of lithic cores found during field surveys between 2003 and 2017.

1.2. Cores

Lithic cores are the result of reduction of raw materials, used for the (primary stage) production of stone tools, either from blades or flakes. In this report we only deal with *flint* cores. Lithic cores could be divided into different types (Patterson, 1975; Odell, 2004); in this overview of cores we distinct: (1) single platform (pyramidal) cores, (2) opposed platform (cylindrical) cores, (3) discoid (or radial) cores and (4) amorphous cores (Odell, 2004; Patterson, 1987). No further subdivisions have been made in this report. Lithic cores could have been re-used as hammerstones or transformed into half fabricates of axes (Waterbolk, 1994). In such cases the original shape is lost, though some blade or flake negatives might be visible at the surface of the core in case of half fabricates. For pyramidal shaped cores, the platform and distal end is decisive for this category. All cores are weight and measured (with maximum width and maximum length), in addition information about the number of removals (or in case of doubt the minimum number of removals, which is indicated). The number of removals is indicated and the length of the last removal, which is often the reason to discard the core because the next stage of reduction would produce blades in far less maximum length. Other things that are noted are the (regional) flint type, (see: Rademakers, 1998) and general context (e.g. from a flint mining area). Attributing a period to surface finds often is difficult in absence of primary contexts; in this case a combination of find location, the length of negatives and appearance of patinas are important determinants to assign a possible period. For many cores the period is almost certain when they are linked to certain flint mining areas such as Banholt or Ryckholt in the Netherlands. Paleolithic cores are not included here; they will be listed in Part 7, (Middle) Paleolithic flint objects, because such cores are *Levallois* cores. Though this report is about a categorical overview of lithic cores, found during field surveys in 2003-2017, some results are discussed in the end of this paper.

Outline

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Entries format

Id-Number with possible former codes, provenance or coordinates (general coordinates: GC)
 Dimensions (L x W in cm, maximum dimensions), weight (in rounded grams)
 Context of discovery (field, forest, soil type, etc.)
 Description with number of removals and length of last removal (all measured in cm)
 Image(s) *format*: dorsal view; ventral view; platform view (*or* side view)
 Context date

1.3. Single platform pyramidal cores

This group is based on properties of both a single platform and in most cases a pyramidal shape. This latter property is not always expressed. In fact, the final shape of a core depends on what remains of it after final reduction, so for this group e.g. the distal shape is not always determined, but unidirectional blows from the platform exclude other core types, such as the opposite platform core.

001 PLC 333 Visé Belgium 50.801009, 5.686604 GC

11.5 x 4.8 300g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. GC = general coordinates, the core has been found somewhere in the center of the field.

Local Hesbaye (*Pietersberg - 1*)¹ flint. Cortex partially present over total length of core. The platform is oblique, with damaged edges. Dorsal side is showing some flake removal, due to initial reduction stage. Largest flake: 10.1 x 1.5. Number of visible negatives: 7. Last flake removal length: 4.2 (step)

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

002 PLC/E PLC 16 Visé Belgium 50.801270, 5.686105

11.5 x 6.1 605g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC/ E indicates the core has been found in the most western part of the field.

Light grey local *Pietersberg 1* flint. The platform is almost straight, slightly inward curved and damaged at the edges. A frost ridge is visible. Some wide flakes have been taken from the upper part of the core, with max. length 4.1 and 2.3 cm.

Largest flake: 11.3 x 1.6; number of visible negatives: 10 ; last flake removal length: 5.4

¹ *St. Pietersberg-1* flint is the name of the local Belgian grey flint type, given by W.M.Felder; see: Rademakers, 1998, pp 188 -189. This flint type is almost the same as *St. Pietersberg -2* but this last type is slightly darker grey. The flint type is thought to be mined from the slopes in the area of PLC. In the field PLC, at the southern part a location has been established, labeled PLCD where the dark grey flint type has been noticed, similar to *St Pietersberg 2*

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

003 PLCB 0211 Visé Belgium 50.800524, 5.686942

11.3 x 7.7 624g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLCB indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

Flint type is local light grey *St Pietersberg -1* flint type. A very little part of the cortex is still visible. A large transversal blow has been given at the distal part of the core. The platform is concave in shape. The largest flake measures 10.6 (the curved one) and in case of a straight negative the length is 8.0; the number of visible negatives is 9 and the last flake removal length: 7.7 cm.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

004 PLC/ E 0213 Visé Belgium 50.801500, 5.686191

10.1 x 8.0 462g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is possibly an open air flint mining area. The code PLCB indicates the core has been found in the most western part of the field.

Local light grey *St. Pietersberg -1* flint type. Platform is only partially processed, because part of it is still covered with cortex. Largest flake: unknown. Number of visible negatives: 6; the last flake removal has a length of 5.1 ending in step. A large transversal blow is visible.

3500 -2100 BC

005 PLC349 0212 Visé Belgium 50.801164, 5.686802 GC

10.9 x 7.0 365g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC indicates the core has been found in the center part of the field.

Local Hesbaye flint type, probably *Pietersberg 1 or 2*. The core has a destructed platform. The core has a covering of patina at the entire surface. Small flake/blade removals are visible between the longer removals. Atypical in appearance compared with 002, 003 and 004. Probably the core has been secondarily used for the production of some flakes. There is a transversal blow at the distal end. Largest flake: 7.0 or probably 8.0, hard to determine. Number of visible negatives: 2 + 1/ of which 2 definite blades. Last flake removal length: not visible

Uncertain period

006PLCB 88 Vise Belgium 50.800598, 5.686797

11.1 x 6.0 548g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLCB indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

Dark grey flint with some cortex. Battered, curved platform with damaged edges. The core has many small stains of which some oxidized. A large transversal blow is visible. Largest flake: 10.9
Number of visible negatives: 10; last flake removal length: 2.5 ending in a deep step fraction.

Neolithic

007 PLC/E 0206 Vise Belgium 50.801164, 5.686143

Length of this broken core: 10.8, width 7.8 603g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC/E indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

The distal end has been broken (unknown whether this has been by accident or deliberately). The flint type is of *St. Pietersberg - 1* type. Platform is half intact, dorsal part has been damaged. The edges of the platform show intense damaging. Largest flake: unknown; number of visible negatives: minimum 5, probably 6. Last flake removal length: double: 4.2 and 4.2

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

008 BB 0208 Visé Belgium 50.800168, 5.686529

11.7 x 10.0 1050g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code (PLC) BB indicates the core has been found in the utmost southern part of the field.

The flint type is of *St. Pietersberg - 1* type. The curved platform edge is damaged; the surface shows flake removals/ adaptation. No cortex at the core. Largest flake: 10.5; number of removals: 11 irregular. Last removal length: not visible by irregularity of removals

Uncertain period

009 PLCB BB 41 Vise Belgium 50.800154, 5.686684

10.1 x 5.1 289g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code (PLC) BB indicates the core has been found in the utmost southern part of the field.

Dark grey *Hesbaye* type flint *Pietersberg 1 or 2* (or local PLCD)² see references. The surface is covered with a black glued substance (raisin?). The core is very pointy. Platform is slightly concave and not very damaged at the edges.

Largest flake: 11 cm but very curved; number of removals: 4. Last removal length: 3.0 ending in hinge

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

010 PLCB 413 Vise Belgium 50.801097, 5.686754

9.7 x 7.5 511g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLCB indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

The flint type is of *St. Pietersberg - 1* type. The core has first been used as a single platform core, later adapted by opposite blows from a partial visible second platform (which originally did not exist). From the original platform large step fractions are visible. Largest flake: 9 cm (of the visible part). Number of removals: from 1st platform 9, from opposite direction 4. The opposite platform almost disappeared by a transversal blow (bulb of percussion is still visible). The last removal length is 2.7

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

² This label PLCD refers to the south western part of the field where a large concentration of dark grey flint has been noticed.

011 PLC 0210 B Vise Belgium 50.800948, 5.686631 GC

8.2 x 6.3 270 g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC/B indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

The flint type is of *St. Pietersberg - 1* type. The largest flake measures 7.7; the number of removals is 8 (+ 2 from dorsal side) while the last removal length is 2.4 and ending in outrepassé. The two small blades from the dorsal side measure (L x W) 4.6 x 2.0 and 3.8 x 2.1. The platform is concave, a total of three small strikes ended in short blades, two of them were wrong and ended in outrepassé.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

012 SG 0215 Eijsderweg Sint Geertruid 50.791566, 5.756413 GC

6.8 x 5.8 133g

From a field near the Rijckholt- St. Geertruid flint mining area and tool production sites

A core fragment. Platform edge intact due to breaking of the core. Secondarily retouched, visible at an edge at the dorsal side. Probably the core served as an *ad hoc* pick before it broke and was discarded. Largest flake: inapplicable; last removal length: inapplicable. Number of removals: 4

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

013 PLCB Visé Belgium 50.800520, 5.686722

9.1 x 5.1 225g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC/B indicates the core has been found in the southern part of the field.

The flint type is local *Pietersberg 1 or 2*. Largest blade negative: 7.9; number of removals: 5; last removal length: 4.3; transverse blow visible. Platform oblique by core rejuvenation and discarded. Some smaller blades have been taken from the core. Patinas at the surface.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

014 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

8.2 x 4.0 148g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin³. The coordinates are general coordinates of a field where excavations have been carried out.

The flint type is typical for the northwestern region of Liège; it's a flint type variable in color between light grey and black with typically many white to grey dots that might vary in dimensions and could cluster together in high density. This core has a very straight platform. Largest flake: 8.8; number of removals: 8; last removal length: 4.5 ending in step, caused by visible pollution. The dorsal part is covered by cortex. Wide (1.6) and narrow (0.5) blades are taken from the core.

Neolithic, Linear Pottery Culture 5400-5000 BC

³ Découvertes et aire de dispersion des villages omaliens en Belgique par J. Hamal -Nandrin, J. Servais et Maria Louis Société Royale Belge d'Anthropologie et de préhistoire pp. 25-125 [PDF](#)

015 AN Anixhe (Belgium) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

7.5 x 3.5 112g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin

The flint type is typical for the northwestern region of Liège. Largest blade negative: 6.2; number of removals: 10 with various widths: 0.8, 0.6, 1.4. Last removal length: 2.1 ending in step. Platform is oblique due to rejuvenation; the original core has been longer.

Neolithic, Linear Pottery Culture 5400-5000 BC

016 SG 0204 Sint Geertruid 50.791539, 5.755984 GC

13.2 x 6.2 515g

From a field in the Neolithic flint mine area of Rijckholt. General coordinates taken from the find location in the field in the southern part of the area.

Rijckholt flint type, the dorsal side with cortex. Largest blade negative: 12.4
Number of removals:8 Last removal length: 6.3. The platform is slightly oblique

(Early) Neolithic

017 BHG Z2 Mheer 50.789452, 5.798566

9.1 x 5.0 283g

From a field South of the Banholtergrubbe, related to mining activities of the Banholt flint mine

Banholt flint, with partially oblique platform due to rejuvenation. Largest flake:

Number of removals: 12

Last removal length *after* rejuvenation of core: 3.4; the distal end was inconvenient for processing.

The distal end has been reshaped, sharpened, probably to serve as a pick (?)

Neolithic (5400-2100 BC)

018 BHG Banholt 50.791947, 5.796935

9.5 x 8.0 635g

From a field adjacent to the Banholt flint mines (Atelier 2)

The core is a fragment in *Banholt* flint type; Largest flake: 10 (only measurable blade negative that has been struck from the *current* platform. Number of removals: 8.

Last removal length: 6.1. The platform has been almost destroyed. The core was only partially processed (abundance of flint, only good quality flint was used)

Neolithic (5400-2100 BC)

019 VRBC Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC

6.9 x 6.0 170g

From a field north of the Neolithic flint mine area of Rijckholt; the general coordinates in this case indicates the exact find location is not further specified.

To be compared with 012/ GS0215. The core is a fragment. Reused flint core. The platform edge has been damaged. The dorsal part contains ca 35 % cortex at the surface. Transverse strikes are visible, probably for re- adaptation to serve as a pick (?). Largest blade negative: 5.9

Number of visible removals: 5

Last removal length(L x W) 2.8 x 2.1

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

020 VRBC Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC

8.0 x 5.8 214g

From the flint mine complex of Rijckholt, north of the mining area

Rijckholt flint with slightly concave platform. The platform and the edges of the platform are damaged. Largest flake: 5.6 (but not original length).

Number of removals: 6 (visible). The dorsal side is only roughly shaped.

Last removal length:inapplicable.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

021 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

8.3 x 5.4 210g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin

Regional flint (Liège). Platform is straight, edges are damaged. The dorsal side has partially cortex at the surface. Largest flake: 8.0; number of removals: 8, irregular blade negatives
Last removal length: inapplicable.

Neolithic (5400-2100 BC)

022 K4 Maaseik (B) 3680, Belgium 51.033009, 5.624250

5.1 x 3.2 77g

From a field not far from Niel - bij – As in Belgium; the field is adjacent (north) to a former brook.

Originally this was a small core; the flint type is *Rijckholt flint*.

Number of blade negatives: 7. The platform has two negatives due to transverse blows and has been damaged.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

023 BHG Banholt Banholt 50.791947, 5.796935 (Atelier 2)

7.8 x 7.6 519g

From a field adjacent to the flint mine area of Banholt, where an atelier has been noticed.

Proximal (top) part of a core. Though two platforms are visible, only one has been used, the second is due to a transversal break. The core has been used to produce relatively wide blades, ranging in width 1.4 – 2.2; half of the core is covered with cortex. The platform is almost horizontal and has damaged edges.

Number of removals: 6

Last removal length: 2.6

Probably Neolithic.

024J EWM Eckelraderweg Sint Geertruid 50.807816, 5.794991

3.0 (2.0) x 5.4 128g

The field is located above what is believed a former marsh or source area. In the vicinity near the *Valkenburgerweg*, round features were noticed with help of satellite images by Google maps, suggesting open air mining; at the field, several other cores have been detected, so this possibly has been some small exploitation point for flint.

Core rejuvenation part, oblique in shape at one side. The flint is probably *Rijckholt* flint or local. One side is battered; the other side is slightly concave opposite to the produced new platform. The bulb of percussion and scar are visible. Number of visible parallel negatives of blades: 8. The part has patinas.

Neolithic (3500-2100 BC)

025 BHG Banholt Banholt 50.792110, 5.796677 (Atelier2)

5.1 x 3.9 155g

From a field west of the flint mines of Banholt

Banholt or *Rijckholt flint*. The battered platform was the *distal* end of a blade core. Largest flake:
Number of removals: 9. Cortex is partially present. Final stage of the core.
Last removal length:

Broad Neolithic

026 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

5.0 x 5.9 105g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin. The general coordinates mark a field where excavations took place in the past.

Destroyed platform. Length of visible negatives is 4.2; these were small blades taken from the core. The type of the core is radial with blades taken from two opposite sides. The distal end is battered, probably the core served as a hammer- stone.

Number of removals: 4 blade negatives, one flake negative

Late Mesolithic – Early Neolithic

027 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

6.8 x 4.3 152g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin

Single platform. Grey flint of unknown provenance, dorsal side has 50 % cortex. Platform is slightly concave. Largest blade negative: 5.9

Number of removals: 4; last removal length: 4.1 ending in step. Two other, different strikes ended in step. The distal end is battered and probably used as hammer-stone.

Late Mesolithic – Early Neolithic

028 IS Schalbruch Selfkant 52538, Germany 51.055313, 5.896718

2.8 x 2.4 17g

From a small elevation in the marsh area of Schalbruch/ IJzeren Bos

Brown unknown flint type, with light grey to white dots. Small core for blades. Largest blade negative: 2.0.

Number of removals: 6, additional flake removals: 6. Blades (L x W) 1.8 x 0.55, 1.5 x 0.7, 2.0 x 0.8

Last removal length: 1.5 ending in step.

Probably Mesolithic

029 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

6.8 x 4.1 118g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin

Regional flint type. The platform is intact, but intact edges. The distal end is damaged (destroyed?) due to secondary use as a hammer. Largest blade negative: 5.2; widths of some negatives: 0.6, 0.7, 0.9, 1.6; the dorsal side has 85 % cortex covering.

Number of removals: 7

Last removal length:

Late Mesolithic – Early Neolithic

030 VRAP Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC

11.2 x 6.1 362g

The general coordinates only indicate in this case the location near the flint mines of Ryckholt. Exact coordinates are known and used for a publication on find spot VRAP (in preparation).

Remains of a core in light grey *Rijckholt* flint. Originally setup of some axe or pick, abandoned. The platform is straight horizontal. The dorsal side is flaked and damaged. Largest blade negative: 9.6; number of blade negatives: 6. The original size of this core must have been larger; the core has been used for the production of wide blades.

Neolithic (3100- 2400 BC)

031 Boch- K Bocholtz (NL) Castle Bocholtz 50.823062, 6.000346

1.8 x 2.9 14g

The field is located south of the Castle of Bocholtz. It is adjacent to the Eijserbeek (brook) and the location probably served as a temporary site

The flint type is wide range of Valkenburg flint. Rejuvenation part of a small blade core Largest flake: Number of removals: 2; platform edge has been damaged.

Unknown period

1.4. Opposed and multi -platform cores

This group contains cores that have strikes, made in opposite direction, often made from two prepared platforms (natural platforms might also occur). Platforms are sometimes (almost) perpendicular or in random position. Platforms could be damaged, oblique or even be destroyed by later actions.

032 SB Aachen Seffent; RWTH Melaten Nord 52074 Aachen, Germany 50.791366, 6.051565 GC (constructed area)

3.4 x 2.3 19g

The field was dominated by large calcareous blocks up to 1-2 meters in cross -section; the typical soil of the field was a so called *rendzina* soil- type, originating from the Weichselian period (Paleolithic) and light brown in color. The field SB and SB2 was a location of much prehistoric activity, from the late Paleolithic – Neolithic period.

Flint is Orsbach/ Vetschau type. The core has two distinguishable platforms. The proximal platform measures 1.8 x 1.1 and 4 visible negatives were taken from it. The distal platform measures 1.2 x 0.6 and 2 visible negatives belong to this platform. Largest blade: 2.7.

Number of removals: 6. Last removal length:0.6 ending in step

Mesolithic- Neolithic

033 PLC 381 Visé Belgium 50.800920, 5.686625

4.5 x 2.7 42g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC indicates the core has been found in the center part of the field.

The core is from local *Pietersberg-1* flint. A small core with blade negatives taken from opposite sides. Largest blade negative: 4.6 (curved), the number of removals is 4. Last blade removal is not visible.

Mesolithic- Neolithic

034 VR Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC

4.5 x 5.8 89g

General coordinates only indicate the core has been found in the Flint mine area of Ryckholt.

Rijckholt flint type. Two platforms are present almost in perpendicular position to each other; the first platform measures 2.8 x 1.2, the other measures 2.0 x 1.4. Largest flake: 3.7/ 3.5. Irregular blades were taken from the core. Some cortex is still at the surface of one side.

Neolithic

035 PLC-C Visé Belgium 50.801524, 5.686609

3.3 x 2.8 28g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC-C indicates the core has been found in the western part of the field.

Local *Pietersberg 1* flint type. Opposite platform core. The number of blade negatives is 10. Largest blade measures 2.8 (x 0.6). Last blade removals are respectively 2.5 and 1.8 both ending in step. Platform 1 measures 2.7 x 1.8, while platform 2 measures 1.7 x 0.9. Platform 1 has no damaged edges indicating rejuvenation, platform 2 has edge damaging end some step fractions.

Number of removals:

Last removal length:

Neolithic

036 Boch Bocholtz Rischerkuijlerweg Simpelveld 50.828224, 5.989188 ± 10m.

5.0 x 2.8 32g

Single find on a field that is sloping into south eastern direction.

Flint type is like flint from the Liège region (Anixhe –Tilice- Liers). The platform is oblique; the core has been used for the production of very small blades. Largest blade negative: 2.9

Number of removals: 9; width of blades 0.5 – 1.0 max in opposite strikes.

The dorsal side is with corroded cortex. Patinas all over the surface

Probably from the Mesolithic

037 VSV2 Vaals Vaals 50.761942, 5.990578

4.9 x 1.9 9g

From a field near and adjacent to the Zieversbeek.

The core has one platform and all sides have been used. Largest flake: 3.5.

Number of removals: 6; last removal length: 2.5 ending in step. One side contains some cortex.

Probably Mesolithic

038 AN Anixhe (B) Juprelle Belgium 50.705219, 5.576492 GC

3.9 x 3.5 74g

From a Linear Pottery Site excavated in 1936 by Hamal – Nandrin.

The platform has been destroyed – two platforms are distinguishable. Only the ventral side has been used, like with many cores. Largest flake: 3. Dorsal side is with ca 50 % cortex.

Number of removals: 5

Last removal length: 2.6

Late Mesolithic- Early Neolithic

039 VRBC2 exact coordinates: Unnamed Road Sint Geertruid 50.799921, 5.747830

3.7 x 2.3 11g

From a field adjacent (north) to VRBC, with finds from the upper Paleolithic.

Fragment of a blade (core) in dark grey (Rijckholt?) flint with brown patinas. Small blade negatives are visible at the dorsal side. The number of visible blade negatives is 3. Probably part of a larger tool (?)

Probably upper Paleolithic to Mesolithic

1.5. Discoid cores

Discoid cores have a discoid shape, which means they are flattened at the dorsal side and often build up to the centre of the ventral side. We find discoid cores in the upper Paleolithic.

040 PLC Visé Belgium 50.801524, 5.686609 GC

5.2 x 5.8 124g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC indicates the core has been found in the center part of the field.

The core is from local *St. Pietersberg 1* flint type. Largest flake: one platform is intact, created by a transverse placed strike. The discoid form could be the result of secondarily adaptation of a pyramidal core. Both flakes and blades are taken from the core. Number of blade removals is 3, the number of flake removals 4. Patinas are equal in appearance over the entire object. Number of removals: 7

Period is unknown

041 SGM Sint Geertruid 50.791267, 5.755984

6.2 x 5.4 105g

From a field in the southern area of the flint mine area of Rijckholt.

Light grey flint, with flake removals, ending in a zigzag - shaped edge. The ventral side also has been flaked and used as a platform. Both flakes and blades have been produced. Largest flake: 2.8. Number of removals at dorsal side: 5; at ventral side: 6. Some worn cortex at ventral side

Typologically late Paleolithic discoid core

042 W1 Aachen Wachtelkopf Aachen Germany 50.779240, 6.023574

3.1 x 2.7 11g

From a field south of the Schneeberg near Aachen, the field has many calcareous chunks and is covered by a thin loess cover. At the field several small adapted flint implements have been detected.

Fragment of a core, discoid shape after break. Brown flint, probably *Lousberg* flint. Two platforms, a total of 6 negatives are visible, 3 taken from each platform. Last removal: 0.9; largest removal 1.9; sharp edges.

Probably Mesolithic

1.6. Cores with cortex handle

These cores are bound to (flint-) mining locations and might have served as tools for decortication, like 'cleaver'-function. The cores appear with a cortex covered rounded butt, oblique shaped sides ending in a cutting edge. (Blade -) negatives are well visible.

043 VRBC Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC
6.5 x 5.1 220g

General coordinates indicate the core has been found on a specific field north of the flint mine area. Rijckholt flint type. The slanted sides run up and form a cutting edge, where the sides were used as a platform. Total number of removals: 9, both flakes and blades; largest removal measures 4.1. The cortex covers 50 % of the surface. The last flake removal ended in a step and measures 2.3.

Probably Neolithic

044 PLCA Visé Belgium 50.801373, 5.687124

8.4 x 4.5 280g

From the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (see references). This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area. The code PLC -A indicates the core has been found in the northern part of the field.

This core is from local flint type *Pietersberg -1*. Two oblique sides are present with blade negatives. One side has served as a platform to get three blades, of which 2 ended in a step fraction. The other side is flaked. The cortex covers nearly half of the total surface of the object. The largest blade negative is 4.1; the total of 8 removals is distributed by 3 blades and 5 flakes.

Probably Neolithic

045 VRBC Sint Geertruid 50.798863, 5.748259 GC

6.8 x 4.5 119g

From a field located north of the flint mines of Rijckholt, used for tool production.

Local *Rijckholt* flint. Two oblique platforms were used for reduction. One side has three blade negatives; the other side has two negatives. The core tool has a sharp zigzag shaped edge. Maximum blade length is 3.3; cortex cover is about 55% of the total surface

Neolithic

046 AND Unnamed Road Slenaken 50.772832, 5.844681

5.7 x 4.2 96g

From a field with loess cover, near a large depression in the area named Anderdel. The location probably has been temporarily used as an extraction/ hunting - camp

Grey flint, from Rijckholt/ Banholt / Eckelrade; irregular flake negatives and 3 blade negatives. Previous platforms have been used again. The total of negatives is 6, (3 blades and 3 flakes), the largest removal is 3.9 while the last flake removal measures 2.7 ending in a step. One battered side indicates a next function as a hammer- stone.

Probably Mesolithic - Neolithic

047 SEF Br (Brunnen) (D) Willkommweg 52074 Aachen, Germany 50.787778, 6.040085 ± 5m
3.2 x 3.0 20g

The find location is at the steep slope above the source area.

Dark variant of Orsbach / Vetschau flint, with a single platform. The total number of flake/ blade removals is 7. The largest negative measures 1.7. The edge of the platform is damaged.

Mesolithic - Neolithic

048 W2 Schneeberg Wachtelkopf (D) Aachen Germany 50.777969, 6.027404

2.8 x 2.7 15g

A field at the so called Wachtelkopf. The soil is loess mixed with many small calcareous chunks.

A grey flint type with white dots of the type of Anixhe- Liers –Tilice. The shape is discoid. The ventral side has 6 removals, of with one pointed blade and one rectangular blade. The dorsal side has 3 negatives, so the total amount of negatives is 9. The largest blade measures 2.1; the dorsal side has some cortex, a last flake removal at this side measures 1.3 and is ending in a step fraction.

Mesolithic - Neolithic

049 K2 Dilsen, Dilserheide (B) Driepaal 3650 Dilsen-Stokkem, Belgium 51.032938, 5.678832

4.1 x 3.1 60g

The find location is a field where excavations have taken place (Neolithic- Bronze Age); the field is located near a former water source. The top soil is sand and in the western part of the field (Pleistocene) gravels dominate. The core has been found in this western part in the gravel – context.

The core is of unknown flint type, probably fluvial (?). Partially it is burned; partially a soft cortex is visible. The platform has damaged edges. A possible opposite platform has been destroyed; evidence for this platform comes from negatives at the core. Number of negatives from platform 1 = 4; number of negatives from platform 2 = 2. Last removal from platform 1 = 1.65 step; platform 2 = 1.8 step.

The patinas indicate a period from late Paleolithic to Mesolithic, as these are different compared with the patinas of Neolithic – Bronze Age flint from the same field.

050 GH Genhout Busselkensweg Beek 50.919053, 5.837668

3.7 x 3.5 35g

Field covered with loess and find spot is near a slight depression

Core in grey flint with white dots. From the dorsal side, 9 flakes have been taken. From the ventral side 2 flakes and a small blade has been taken according to the visible negatives. Flake lengths e.g. 3.0 / 2.8; micro- blade 1.2 x 0.5. Opposite to a straight side is a sharp edge. The cortex covers <10 % of the surface.

Probably late Paleolithic – Mesolithic

1.7. Amorphous cores

This group is only represented by one typical core. Most amorphous cores found in field surveys from the region have little possibilities to attribute to a period and lack information on tool production (

e.g. cores that have been used to produce a single flake, or have irregular shapes, which are very hard to define). An example is the following core from the prehistoric (Mesolithic) site at Aachen – Seffent *Wilkinsberg* (meaning: ‘source hill’) in Germany, showing cores that also might have been deliberately produced to shape some large tool; blade cores often have been re-used as hammer stones in tool production, examples of such “recycled cores” will be presented in the next part of this series.

051 SB2 Aachen Seffent (D) Aachen 52074, Germany 50.791414, 6.052467 GC (reconstructed area)
8.2 x 5.8 306g

The field was adjacent to SB (east) and was slightly sloping to the east. Calcareous chunks and a *rendzina* type soil are the main characteristics. Nearby a setup of a Neolithic axe in *Lousberg* flint has been found.

Core in local light variant *Vetschau / Orsbach flint* with some cortex. Irregular flakes have been taken from the core, most of them would have been useless; the primary goal must have been ‘shaping’. The core has one ‘backed side’ opposite to a more sharp side, probably served as some wedge. This core is showing the more diffuse line between cores that have been used in lithic reduction for the production of blades/ flakes and adapted cores for different purposes, like wedges, hammer- stones or setups of axes. The next part in this series (2b) is about hammer- stones.

Probably from the Neolithic

2. Some results

As expected in a flint rich area, we find many cores in the fields that were discarded after use. Only one site is rich in cores of identical *Pietersberg 1* flint type: the PLC Riemst Caestert / Visé Caster prehistoric site (in the Belgian Walloon territory); see cores numbers 001-011, 013, 022, 033, 035, 040 and 044. This site is believed to be an open air flint mining area, the seventeen cores are just a part of many cores that have been produced at the site. During prospections many other cores have been noticed but not sampled. The exploitation point has been described as a *find location* of flint tools in the *Pietersberg 1* flint type found by Mr. and Mrs. Brand in 1973 (Rademakers, 1998, pp.188-189, number 27). Additional finds at the location, like hammer- stones and a mining pick in local *Pietersberg 1* flint confirm local tool production, especially the production of (wider) blades. From satellite images made by Google Maps, round features with cross - section dimensions of about 4-6 m. were visible and suggesting we deal with local open air mining activities, determining a local exploitation point of the *Pietersberg 1* flint type with additional ateliers for tool production (Groen, 2014). It is noticed that a transversal blow has been given at the distal part of many discarded flint cores both from the Visé -Caster site and at Ryckholt. Maybe this was a ‘mark’ to indicate the core was useless for further tool production.

The *Pietersberg 2* flint type has been localized at the top of a slope of the Meuse River, where in two separate ateliers several adapted flint objects have been confirmed.

The Anixhe – Liers site in the Belgian *Halembaye* region is a site where tool production played a major role- many cores have been found here (examples in this report: 014, 015, 021, 026, 027, 029, 038) which are believed to be from the transitional phase between Late Mesolithic and early Neolithic (Linear Pottery Culture). The cores have been described by Nandrin (Nandrin, 1936) as cores of a long pyramidal type. The provenance of this flint type is unknown, but is believed to be from the region of Liège in Belgium.

3. References

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Outline of this series

(Expected from 2018 without end date)

Note: date of publication is not consecutively by number in this list and is depending on depot, so the order of publications may vary. All parts will show a *selection* of important finds.

FLINT & NATURAL STONE

Part 1: Flint axes and picks

Part 2a: Flint cores

Part 2b: Hammerstones

Part 3: Polishing stones/ various natural stones

Part 4a: Neolithic flint tools on blades

Part 4b: Neolithic flint tools on flakes

Part 5: Various Neolithic objects

Part 6: Mesolithic flint objects

Part 7: (Middle) Paleolithic flint objects

Part 8: Non - flint stone tools

POTTERY SHARDS

Part 1: Selection of Prehistoric pottery

Part 2: Selection of Roman pottery

Part 3: Selection of Stoneware pottery

Part 4: Selection of Medieval – sub recent pottery

Part 5: Selection of Building ceramics

METAL FINDS (not detector finds)

Part 1: Coins

Part 2: Various metal objects

BONE/ ORGANIC

Part 1: Bones

Part 2: Loam, charcoal

GLASS

Part 1: Selection of glass and opaque glass finds (beads, etc)

MISCELENEOUS

Part 1: various uncategorized objects

All objects in this series are for educational purpose.